

Relationship between Viscosities and the Composition of Binary Solutions

V. R. Shastry, H. G. Asawa, and N. S. Sahani

A great deal of work¹ has been done to correlate viscosities of binary solutions with their concentrations, but no relation of a simple nature and wide applicability appears to be available in the literature. In the present communication, derivation of a simple relationship from altogether a new angle, with the help of rheochor, has been attempted.

Hammic and Andrew's mixture law equation² in the case of rheochor³ can be written as:

$$R_m = x R_s + (1-x) R_S \quad \dots \quad (I)$$

where R refers to rheochor and the suffixes m , s , and S refer respectively to solution, solute, and solvent; x is the molar fraction of the solute.

Equation (I) on slight rearrangement takes the form:

$$x = \frac{1}{R_s - R_S} \cdot R_m - \frac{R_S}{R_s - R_S} \quad \dots \quad (II)$$

Since R_s and R_S are constants, equation (II) can be represented as:

$$x = K_1 \cdot R_m - K_2 \quad \dots \quad (III)$$

But according to Hammic and Andrew² and Bhagwat *et al.*³,

$$R_m = \frac{M_m \eta_m^{1/3}}{D_m} = V_m \eta_m^{1/3} \quad \dots \quad (IV)$$

where M_m is the mean molecular weight of the mixture and is given by

$$M_m = x M_s + (1-x) M_S$$

D_m = density of the mixture.

If therefore R_m is substituted by $V_m \eta_m^{1/3}$ in equations (III) and (IV), we get the relationship:

$$x = K_1 (V_m \eta_m^{1/3}) - K_2 \quad \dots \quad (V)$$

1. Partington, "An Advanced Treatise on Physical Chemistry", Vol 2, Longmans, 1951, pp. 115-124.

2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 754.

3. Bhagwat *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 249; 1952, 29, 303; 1943, 20, 165; 1948, 25, 275; 1949, 26, 533, *et seq.*

In the above series of the equations, the relation (V) evidently shows that the plot of x against $V_m \eta_m^{1/6}$ should be a straight line, with a slope $K_1 = 1/(R_1 - R_2)$.

FIG. 1

In a forthcoming communication the results on the solutions of electrolytes in water and those of organic solvents will be presented. Here we are submitting the data from the work of Bhagwat and Subnis⁴ in Table I in the case of toluene in methanol. The representative graph in Fig. 1 shows clearly the validity of the linear equation (V).

TABLE I

x .	D_m .	η_m .	M_m .	$V_m \eta_m^{1/6}$.	dx .	$dV_m \eta_m^{1/6}$.	$\frac{dV_m \eta_m^{1/6}}{dx}$
0.0000	0.7903	5.60	32.00	50.30	..	..	..
0.1636	0.8179	5.68	41.84	63.84	0.1636	13.64	82.7
0.3517	0.8307	5.60	53.15	79.05	0.1881	15.21	80.8
0.5095	0.8392	5.44	62.66	92.26	0.1578	13.21	84.3
0.6126	0.8447	5.39	68.85	100.40	0.1031	8.35	80.9
0.7321	0.8494	5.32	76.04	110.22	0.1195	9.66	80.8

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CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
HOLKAR SCIENCE COLLEGE,
INDORE.

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